

SURVEY

The i-SOMPE project collected a list and descriptions of 58 innovative soil management practices (SMPs) used across Europe

BARRIERS...

For adopting innovative SMPs at EU scale appropriate guidelines, smoothly running networks and interaction between stakeholders, as well as liquidity and directed financial incentives are essential.

...AND OPPORTUNITIES

Many European farmers are willing to introduce innovations. Adoption of low-input and innovative SMPs might enhance agroecosystem resilience to environmental stress, to improve sustainability of food production and to preserve soils from degradation

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.14974587](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14974587)

AUTHORS

Frédéric Vanwindekens, Olivier Heller, Claudia Di Bene, Pasquale Nino, Bruno Huyghebaert (2022)

AN INVENTORY OF MAIN SOIL PRACTICES FOR MANAGING EUROPEAN AGROECOSYSTEMS

18 - Cover crops

i-SOMPE - Adoption of soil management practices

An overview of innovative soil management practices at European scale is needed. The i-SOMPE project provided a complete inventory of innovative soil management practices (SMPs).

A hundred practices were described regarding environmental limits in terms of farming systems, land use, site and soils, as well as evaluating their application and potential impacts and drafting their ability for tackling main soil challenges.

EJP SOIL INNOVATION HIGHLIGHTS

TOWARDS CLIMATE-SMART SUSTAINABLE MANAGEMENT OF AGRICULTURAL SOILS

EJP SOIL is a European Joint Programme on Agricultural Soil Management addressing key societal challenges including climate change and future food supply. <https://ejpsoil.eu/>

The goal is to improve the understanding of agricultural soil management by finding synergies in research, strengthening research communities and raising public awareness.

1100+ experts, 24 countries, addressing multiple aspects of soil management across different European agroecosystems.

EJP SOIL FUNDED PROJECT i-SoMPE

The i-SoMPE project aims to document innovative soil management practices across Europe. Some innovative soil management and farming practices can address major EJP SOIL targets “good agricultural soil management for: climate change mitigation and adaptation, sustainable production, ecosystem services and less soil degradation”.

PROJECT COORDINATOR

Frederic Vanwindekens

f.vanwindekens@cra.wallonie.be

TARGET EJP SOIL EXPECTED IMPACT AND EU MISSION SOIL OBJECTIVES

Fostering understanding of soil management and its influence on climate change mitigation and adaptation, sustainable agricultural production and environment. Develop and demonstrate region- and context-specific fertilization practices (soil, water and pedo-climatic conditions) **Mission SOIL**: conserve soil organic carbon stocks, prevent erosion, improve soil structure to enhance soil biodiversity

HIGHLIGHT FACTS FROM:

EJP SOIL funded project:
i-SoMPE

Applicability:
all climatic zones according to
Metzger et al. (2005)
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1466-822X.2005.00190.x>

EJP SOIL has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme: Grant agreement No 862695

